

TESTS OF THE RECALIBRATION PERIOD OF A DRIFTING INSTRUMENT

Walter Liggett

National Bureau of Standards, Gaithersburg, MD 20899

ABSTRACT

The use of a drifting instrument requires that an adequately short recalibration period be chosen. After several periods, the calibration data can be used to test the adequacy of the choice. This paper discusses statistical tests of the recalibration period and applies these tests to continuous analyzers for sulfur dioxide. These tests check the sequence of calibrations for evidence of rapid drift-rate changes, which are obscured by random measurement error and by slow drift-rate changes for which the recalibration period is adequate. This paper presents two tests, a test of the second differences of the calibration sequence for normality and a test of the upper part of the spectrum for flatness. Both of these tests are needed because they have different power against different alternatives to constant drift rate. This paper illustrates these tests with two sequences each consisting of about fifty recalibrations of a sulfur dioxide analyzer. Also, the power of the tests and some approximations made in their formulation are investigated by Monte Carlo experiments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Much can be learned about a drifting instrument from the sequence of recalibrations needed to track the time variation of the calibration curve. The calibration curve of an instrument specifies the deterministic part of the relation between the instrument response and the quantity to be measured. For a drifting instrument, this curve changes with time. The calibration curve is estimated from the responses of the instrument to known standards. For a drifting instrument that is in continuous use, not only the calibration curve at the times of recalibration but also the calibration curve at times between recalibrations must be estimated. The sets of instrument responses from successive recalibrations form time sequences that can provide more than an estimate of the time variation of the calibration curve. These sequences can indicate that the period between recalibrations is too long in light of changes in the drift rate of the instrument. These sequences can also reveal problems with the random error that is part of the instrument response.

In the case considered in this paper, the instrument response is the sum of a linear function

of the quantity to be measured and random error. This linear function is the calibration curve. Drift in the instrument corresponds to changes in the intercept or slope of this linear function with time. For simplicity, we consider the case in which two calibration standards are used. The data analysis methods discussed can be generalized to more than two standards. For concreteness, let the quantity to be measured be the concentration of some analyte, and let one of the standards have zero concentration and the other concentration X . In the calibration performed at time T_t , where $t = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, the two instrument responses observed are

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{0t} &= \alpha_t + \epsilon_{0t} \\ Y_{1t} &= \alpha_t + \beta_t X + \epsilon_{1t}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The parameters α_t and β_t are the time-varying intercept and slope of the calibration curve. The random error components, ϵ_{0t} and ϵ_{1t} , considered as a bivariate sequence indexed by t , are independent and identically distributed.

The data analysis methods discussed in this paper are illustrated with calibration sequences from two instruments for continuously monitoring sulfur dioxide in the atmosphere.¹ To fix ideas and motivate the discussion, we introduce these sequences now. Note, however, that little in this paper is peculiar to this application. Figures 1 and 2 show the sequences considered, which consist of 55 and 57 calibrations, respectively, generally made at two or three day intervals. The upper and lower panels show, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} A_t &= Y_{0t} \\ B_t &= (Y_{1t} - Y_{0t})/X. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the upper panel, the zero response A_t is centered and scaled to parts per billion on the basis of A_0 and B_0 , the results of the first calibration. In the lower panel, the span B_t is given as percent deviation from B_0 . The calibration data from sulfur dioxide analyzers are usually given in this form. As discussed in more detail below, Figures 1 and 2 show various manifestations of instrument drift.

Do the sequences shown in Figures 1 and 2 show that the period between recalibrations is too long? This question has a modeling aspect and an inferential aspect. The modeling aspect can be phrased in terms of Equation 1. The question is whether the period is so long that the intercept

Figure 1. Calibration Sequences from Instrument 1.

and slope of the calibration curve cannot be obtained for all times from the intercepts α_t and slopes β_t at the calibration times. If we could observe the values α_t and β_t directly, then we could ask whether these values could be interpolated with a smooth function. Because of the random noise, we must ask whether the observed sequences of instrument responses are consistent with a model composed of a smooth function and random noise. This question is still, of course, ambiguous because we have not defined what we mean by a smooth function. The inferential aspect involves the probability that we will say the period between recalibrations is too long when the period is adequate. For monitoring instruments located in the field, the economic consequences of shortening the recalibration period are considerable. This inferential aspect is important in this paper.

Since the question of the recalibration period involves modeling by a smooth function and random error, approaches generally consist of two steps, decomposition of the time sequences of instrument responses into a smooth part and a rough (or rapidly varying) part and a decision on whether the rough part can be attributed to the random noise. Since we are interested in the inferential aspects of the question, we must choose a decomposition method that allows inference on the rough part. The two methods that we consider below satisfy this requirement.

Figure 2. Calibration Sequences from Instrument 2.

The first approach we consider is examination of the second differences of sequences of responses to the same calibration standard. Second differencing eliminates any linear trend and leaves only variations due to changes in the drift rate and variations due to the random error. If changes in the drift rate are small as they must be for the recalibration period to be adequate, then the second differences should appear to be the second differences of a series of independent variates. If we add the assumption that the random error is normal, then we have a null hypothesis that we can test. This approach is discussed in Section 2.

The second approach we consider is examination of the power spectrum of the sequence of responses. If the calibration curve changes slowly, then the high-frequency part of the spectrum should be due only to the random error and should appear to be flat, that is, independent of frequency. This approach is discussed in Section 3.

We consider both approaches because, as shown in Section 4, the first has more power against a few abrupt changes in the drift rate, and the second has more power against more frequent, smaller changes. Were we primarily interested in an estimate of the time variation of the calibration curve, then we would have to consider three other approaches, spline fitting,² Kalman filtering,³ and robust smoothing.⁴ A comparison with these approaches is beyond the scope of this paper.

2. SECOND DIFFERENCE ANALYSIS

Consider the sequences $\{Y_{0t}\}$ and $\{Y_{1t}\}$ of instrument responses, which are observed at the times $\{T_t\}$. In computing the second differences of these sequences, we allow for the fact that the periods between calibrations are not all of the same length. We take the second differences to be the differences between the drift rates observed in adjacent periods. We compute the drift rate for a period from the actual calibration times. The second differences are given by

$$D_{i,t} = \frac{Y_{i,t+1} - Y_{i,t}}{T_{t+1} - T_t} - \frac{Y_{i,t} - Y_{i,t-1}}{T_t - T_{t-1}}, \quad (3)$$

where $i = 0, 1$ and $t = 1, 2, \dots, n-2$. These second differences are appropriate if the causes of the drift operate continuously and produce trends that are linear in clock time. Note, however, that our approach does require that the periods between calibrations be nearly equal since an assumption of our test is that the $D_{i,t}$ have equal variances.

Our criterion for the recalibration period is that it be short enough to allow the time variation of the intercept and slope of the calibration curve to be portrayed by the intercepts and slopes at the calibration times. If this is to be true, then the second differences of the sequences $\{\alpha_t\}$ and $\{\alpha_t + \beta_t X\}$ must be nearly zero. Conversely, large values of these second differences indicate large changes in the drift rate that can only be accurately tracked by more closely spaced calibration times.

The basis for our approach is that the second differences $D_{i,t}$ are so dominated by the random error that we can ignore the contribution from the second differences of the calibration curve. The consequence of this implicit comparison is that for the same sequence of calibration curves, our conclusion will depend on the size of the random error. That the noise might mask large variations in the calibration curve seems inevitable. That our approach might be too sensitive for instruments with little random error is at least conceivable.

Our approach is to rearrange each series of second differences into subseries consisting of every third point and to test each subseries for normality. We choose every third point because second differencing a series of independent variates induces dependence over one and two periods. The j th subseries for instrument response i is given by

$$\bar{D}_{ijk} = D_{i,3k-j+1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \bar{n}_j, \quad (4)$$

where $i = 0, 1$; $j = 1, 2, 3$; and $\bar{n}_j = [(n+j-3)/3]$. If the random error dominates the second differences, if the random error is normal, and if the calibration periods are all the same, then each subseries will contain independent, identically-distributed, normal variates. This is the basis of our test. Note that our test will also detect outliers in the random error.

Our choice of test is the probability plot

correlation coefficient test for normality.⁵ Other choices might be more effective in some applications. The probability plot correlation coefficient is given by

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\sum_k M_{jk} (\bar{D}_{ij(k)} - \bar{D}_{ij.})}{[(\sum_k M_{jk}^2)(\sum_k (\bar{D}_{ijk} - \bar{D}_{ij.})^2)]^{1/2}}, \quad (5)$$

where M_{jk} is the median of the k th order statistic in a sample of \bar{n}_j normal variates, $\bar{D}_{ij(k)}$ is the k th largest value in the j th subseries, and $\bar{D}_{ij.}$ is the mean of the j th subseries. An algorithm for computing M_{jk} and critical points for r_{ij} are given by Filliben.⁵ The choice of critical point must account for the fact that three subseries are being tested. To do this, we use the Bonferroni inequality to justify choosing critical points for the significance level $\alpha/3$ when an overall significance level of α is desired.

Consider now the sequences shown in Figures 1 and 2. In the application of the methods in this paper to sulfur dioxide analyzers, two approximations should be noted. First, these analyzers were adjusted physically. The effect of these adjustments must be estimated from the calibrations made immediately before and immediately after the adjustment, and then this effect must be removed from the sequence of observed responses. In our analysis of the responses, we have not taken into account the added random error that accompanies estimation of the effect of the physical adjustments. Second, the non-zero standard may vary from calibration to calibration. Because we consider B_t instead of Y_{1t} , this variation only changes the variance of the random error in B_t . We do not take this variation into account.

For the sequences in Figure 1, the second-difference test of the zero response is significant at the 0.015 level, but the test of the span is not significant at the 0.150 level. The subseries specified by Equation 4, which contain 17, 18, and 18 points respectively, give values of the probability plot correlation coefficient of 0.918, 0.992, and 0.882 for the zero response and 0.967, 0.991, and 0.991 for the span. The zero response is significant at the 0.015 level because 0.882 is below the critical point 0.907, which for a single sample corresponds to a significance level of 0.005. The span is not significant at the 0.150 level because none of the three values is below the corresponding critical point for a single-sample significance level of 0.05. As indicated in Figure 1, the zero response shows both jumps (the points labeled 1 and 4) and outliers (the points labeled 2, 3, and 5). The jumps might be interpreted as abrupt shifts in the calibration curve. The outliers might be interpreted as part of the random error. Both the jumps and the outliers suggest the need for improvement in the instrument and the associated measurement procedures.

For the sequences in Figure 2, the test of the zero response is significant at the 0.075 level, but the test of the span is not significant at the 0.150 level. The subseries, which contain 18, 18, and 19 points respectively, give values of the probability

plot correlation coefficient of 0.942, 0.982, and 0.920 for the zero response and 0.985, 0.954, and 0.951 for the span. Nevertheless, as indicated, both sequences show a large jump. This instrument was refurbished after day 129. This seems to have reduced the size of the random error in the zero response and perhaps in the span.

3. SPECTRAL ANALYSIS

Small second differences are not the only basis for judging whether the recalibration period is short enough to allow the time variation of the intercept and slope of the calibration curve to be portrayed by the intercepts and slopes at the calibration times. Another basis can be formulated by regarding the intercept and slope as stationary random processes with spectra that are zero above some frequency. Four times this frequency is the minimum acceptable recalibration frequency. This condition is discussed by Tick and Shaman.⁶ We can test for this condition using the upper half of the (multivariate) power spectrum. If the condition holds, then this part of the power spectrum should not be influenced by changes in the calibration curve but only by the random error. Since the spectrum of the random error is independent of frequency, the upper half of the power spectrum of the calibration sequences should be independent of frequency.

To obtain an estimate of the power spectrum that is appropriate for our test, we must adjust the data before Fourier transformation. This adjustment consists of three steps, outlier removal, linear trend removal, and tapering. Outliers, which are individual points that differ from their neighbors by a large amount, generally contribute to the spectrum at all frequencies and thus mask the changes with frequency that we wish to detect. Linear trends, although they are a form of time variation that can be tracked by linear interpolation, contribute to the upper half of the spectrum. For these reasons, we apply a procedure for outlier and trend removal. Because of drift, the lower half of the power spectrum will be higher than the upper half. To prevent the lower half from biasing the upper half, we taper the calibration sequences after outlier and trend removal. Thomson⁷ provides a detailed discussion of these considerations.

To remove outliers, we identify sequences of three points that give large second differences and then replace the middle point of the three with the median of the three. Identification of large second differences requires a threshold with which to make comparisons. The threshold we choose is based on the ordered second differences and order statistic medians with which we computed the probability plot correlation coefficient. Dropping the dependence of \bar{n} on j from our notation, we let $q = [\bar{n}/4]$. The slope of the line through $(M_{j,q+1}, \bar{D}_{ij(q+1)})$ and $(M_{j,\bar{n}-q}, \bar{D}_{ij(\bar{n}-q)})$ provides an estimate of the standard deviation of the second differences that is not influenced by a few large values. Averaging these estimates for the three subseries gives

$$\bar{s}_i = (1/3) \sum_j \frac{\bar{D}_{ij(\bar{n}-q)} - \bar{D}_{ij(q+1)}}{M_{j,\bar{n}-q} - M_{j,q+1}} \quad (6)$$

Whenever $|D_{i,t}| > 2.5\bar{s}_i$, we substitute for Y_{it} the median of $Y_{i,t-1}$, $Y_{i,t}$, and $Y_{i,t+1}$. The median seems like the right substitute because a series of three that is increasing or decreasing will not be affected however steep the slope whereas a single value that stands out from its neighbors will be changed to the value of its closest neighbor. Thus, abrupt changes in the drift rate are not altered but outliers are replaced. In Figures 1 and 2, the points altered are the ones indicated. The zero response in Figure 1 illustrates this procedure. The points labeled 1 and 4 are not altered since they correspond to jumps, but the points labeled 2, 3 and 5 are altered.

After removing outliers, we remove a linear trend fitted by least squares. We fit $\{T_t\}$ to $\{\bar{Y}_{0t}\}$ and $\{\bar{Y}_{1t}\}$, where the $\bar{}$ indicates that the outlier correction procedure has been applied. The estimates of the trend parameters for \bar{Y}_{it} are denoted by (a_i, b_i) , $i = 0, 1$. The result of the detrending is

$$Z_{it} = \bar{Y}_{it} - a_i - b_i T_t \quad (7)$$

The tapering function that we adopt is the one usually recommended.⁸ Let $q_h = [n/10]+1$. The tapering function is given by

$$h_t = \begin{cases} (1 - \cos(\pi(t+1)/q_h))/2 & 0 \leq t < q_h-1 \\ 1 & q_h-1 \leq t \leq n-q_h \\ (1 - \cos(\pi(n-t)/q_h))/2 & n-q_h < t \leq n-1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

We spectrum analyze $h_t Z_{it}$.

In our spectral analysis, we treat the recalibration periods as equal. The periods must be approximately equal since variations in the period might make drift with a slowly-varying rate look more rapidly varying. More complete removal of large, low frequency variations than is provided by removal of a linear trend will alleviate this problem in some cases.

Spectral analysis consists of computation of the finite Fourier transform

$$nJ_i(2\pi f) = \sum_{t=0}^{n-1} h_t Z_{it} \exp(-j 2\pi f t), \quad (9)$$

and formation of the periodogram

$$I(2\pi f) = n^2 \left(2\pi \sum_{t=0}^{n-1} h_t^2 \right)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} J_0 J_0^* & J_0 J_1^* \\ J_0^* J_1 & J_1 J_1^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

For our flatness test, we use only the frequencies for which $nf = [n/4]$, $[n/4]+1$, ..., $[(n-1)/2]$. We exclude $f = 0.5$ because $I(\pi)$ does not have the same distribution as $I(2\pi f)$ for $0 < f < 0.5$.

For $[n/4] \leq nf \leq [(n-1)/2]$, the periodogram should not depend on f except for the variations due to randomness. To test this hypothesis, we compare

the matrix

$$S_0 = \sum_{j=[n/4]}^{[(n-1)/2]} I(2\pi j/n) \quad (11)$$

with

$$S(N) = \sum_{j=[n/4]}^{[n/4]+N-1} I(2\pi j/n), \quad (12)$$

where $1 \leq N \leq N_0-1$ and $N_0 = [(n-1)/2] - [n/4] + 1$. The comparison is made by judging the size of the eigenvalues of $S(N)$ with respect to S_0 . The eigenvalues of $S(N)$ with respect to S_0 are the values of λ that satisfy

$$\det(S(N) - \lambda S_0) = 0. \quad (13)$$

For each value of N , there are two solutions, which we denote by $\lambda_1(N)$ and $\lambda_2(N)$ ($\lambda_1(N) \geq \lambda_2(N)$). Unless the dependence on N is needed for clarity, we drop it from our notation. If $I(2\pi f)$ does not depend on f , then $\lambda_1(N) = \lambda_2(N) = N/N_0$.

Various critical regions for these eigenvalues can be proposed. However, distributional results that allow the corresponding significance levels to be obtained are often unavailable. Distributional results for a single value of N are provided by Khatri.⁹ Consider the test which rejects the null hypothesis (and concludes that the recalibration period is too long) if $\lambda_1 > v$ or if $\lambda_2 < u$. The significance level for this test is given by

$$1 - \text{Prob}(u \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_1 \leq v) = 1 + \det(H_1),$$

$$H_1 = \begin{pmatrix} G(N, N_0 - N) & (N_0 - 1)G(N, N_0 - N - 1) \\ G(N - 1, N_0 - N) & (N_0 - 2)G(N - 1, N_0 - N - 1) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$G(n_1, n_2) = I_v(n_1, n_2) - I_u(n_1, n_2), \quad (14)$$

where $2 \leq N \leq N_0 - 2$ and $I_x(n_1, n_2)$ is the incomplete beta function.¹⁰ Some significance levels for this test when $N = [N_0/2]$ are

N_0	$u, v =$		
	.10, .90	.15, .85	.20, .80
12	.015	.081	.229
13	.014	.076	.216
14	.006	.044	.155
15	.006	.041	.147
16	.002	.023	.104
17	.002	.022	.099
18	.001	.012	.070
19	.001	.012	.066
20	--	.007	.046
21	--	.006	.044
22	--	.004	.031

Distributional results for some tests involving two values of N are provided by Liggett.¹¹ Consider two values of N , N_1 and N_2 , that satisfy $2 \leq N_2 \leq N_1 - 2$ and $N_1 \leq N_0 - 2$. Consider the test that rejects the null hypothesis if $\lambda_1(N_2) > 0.5$ or $\lambda_2(N_1) < 0.5$. The significance level for this test is given

by

$$1 - \text{Prob}(\lambda_1(N_2) \leq .5 \text{ and } \lambda_2(N_1) \geq .5) = 1 + 2 \frac{-2N_0+2}{\det(H_2)},$$

$$H_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 2^{i+j-2} & N_1 - N_2 - 1 & (N_0 - i)! \\ \sum_{k=0}^{N_1 - N_2 - 1} & & (N_1 - i - k)! (N_0 - N_1 - j + 1 + k)! \end{pmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where H_2 is a 2×2 matrix. Some significance levels for this test when $N_2 = N_0 - N_1$ are

N_0	$N_2 = N_0 - N_1 =$		
	2	3	4
12	.101	.373	--
13	.061	.256	--
14	.036	.170	.469
15	.021	.110	.342
16	.012	.070	.241
17	.007	.043	.164
18	.004	.027	.110
19	.002	.016	.072
20	.001	.010	.046
21	.001	.006	.029
22	--	.003	.018

For the data shown in Figures 1 and 2, neither of the tests is convincing for the first instrument, but the second test is significant for the second instrument. For these cases, we have $N_0 = 15$. The eigenvalues needed for the tests are $\lambda_1(2)$, $\lambda_1(3)$, $\lambda_2(7)$, $\lambda_1(7)$, $\lambda_2(12)$, $\lambda_2(13)$. For the first instrument, these eigenvalues are .148, .314, .387, .811, .844, and .850, respectively. For the second instrument, these eigenvalues are .579, .600, .400, .743, .678, and .714, respectively. For the first instrument, the eigenvalue $\lambda_1(7)$ is significant at the 0.147 level by the first test. For the second instrument, the eigenvalue $\lambda_1(2)$ is significant at the 0.021 level by the second test.

4. MONTE CARLO EXPERIMENTS

Monte Carlo experiments performed on the tests discussed above serve to verify that the significance levels claimed are actually achieved despite our approximations. These experiments also illustrate the power of these tests against various alternatives. We consider three situations. In the first, the two sequences are each 56 random variates that are independent and normal with mean 0 and variance 1. In the second, one sequence is 56 random variates as in the first situation but the second is 56 consecutive points from the autoregressive process

$$Y_{1,t} = 0.75Y_{1,t-1} - 0.50Y_{1,t-2} + \epsilon_{1t}, \quad (16)$$

where the ϵ_{1t} are independent and normal with mean 0 and variance 1. This process is used by Box and Jenkins¹² as an example. The spectrum of this process peaks at $f = 0.155$. Between $f = 0.25$ and $f = 0.50$, the spectrum drops by a factor of 13/81. In the third situation, one sequence is again 56 random variates as in the first situation but the second consists of 56 random variates plus a process which jumps 8 units with probability 0.05

at each calibration time. In other words, the second sequence is given by

$$Y_{1,t} = x_t + \varepsilon_{1t}, \quad x_t = x_{t-1} + a_t, \quad (17)$$

where the a_t are independent and take on two values, 8 and 0, with probabilities 0.05 and 0.95.

We applied the tests as discussed above except that we let $N_0 = 15$ in the spectral tests so that the lowest frequency included is 13/56. The numbers of times the null hypotheses were rejected in 1000 independent runs are

TEST	RANDOM	AUTOREG	JUMP
$\min_j r_{0j} < .945$	112	121	125
$\min_j r_{1j} < .945$	139	133	547
$\min_j r_{0j} < .919$	31	26	22
$\min_j r_{1j} < .919$	28	24	271
$\lambda_2(7) < .15$ or $\lambda_1(7) > .85$	62	246	42
$\lambda_1(2) > .5$ or $\lambda_2(13) < .5$	34	309	63
$\lambda_1(3) > .5$ or $\lambda_2(12) < .5$	149	601	213

The runs for the first situation show that the significance levels are close to those claimed. Consider first the second difference test, which in this case is based on subsamples each of length 18. For a single series of length 18, the probability plot correlation coefficient critical point for a significance level of 0.05 is .945 and for a level of 0.01 is .919. Combining the results of the two sequences, we have 2000 runs. Of these runs, at least one subsample was below .945 in 251 cases and at least one subsample was below .919 in 59 cases. The result for the higher critical point indicates a significance level somewhat below the level obtained from the Bonferroni inequality, which is 0.15. The result for the lower critical point is very close to the Bonferroni level. The significance levels for the spectral tests show that the manipulation of the series increases the level somewhat. The spectral test with critical region $\lambda_2(7) < .15$ or $\lambda_1(7) > .85$ is significant in 62 runs although the level is supposed to be .041. The spectral test with critical region $\lambda_1(2) > .5$ or $\lambda_2(13) < .5$ is significant in 34 runs although the level is supposed to be .021. The spectral test with critical region $\lambda_1(3) > .5$ or $\lambda_2(12) < .5$ is significant in 149 runs although the level is supposed to be 0.110. These spectral results are more in line with $N_0 = 14$ than $N_0 = 15$. This sort of reduction is expected from the use of tapering.

The other two situations provide examples of the power of the tests. These examples show that the second difference tests are needed to detect jumps and that the spectral tests are needed to detect non-flat spectra. In the thousand runs with the autoregressive process as the second sequence, the test $\min_j r_{ij} < .945$ rejected the null hypothesis in 121 runs for the first sequence and in 133 runs for the second sequence. The corresponding result for the critical point .919 is 26 and 24 runs, respectively. This shows that this test has almost no power against this autoregressive process. On the other hand, the three spectral tests rejected the null hypothesis in 246, 309, and 601 runs respectively. In the thousand runs with the jump

process as the second sequence, the test $\min_j r_{ij} < .945$ rejected the null hypothesis in 125 runs for the first sequence and in 547 runs for the second sequence. The corresponding result for the critical point .919 is 22 and 271 runs, respectively. On the other hand, the three spectral tests rejected the null hypothesis in 42, 63, and 213 runs, respectively. This shows that the spectral tests have little power against jumps.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Although the research described in this paper has been funded in part by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency under IAG DW-13930628-01-0, Subagreement 8, with the National Bureau of Standards, it has not been subjected to the Agency's peer and administrative review and therefore may not necessarily reflect the views of the Agency and no official endorsement should be inferred.

REFERENCES

1. Michie, R. M., Jr.; McElroy, F. F.; Sexton, F. W.; Thompson, V. L. Performance test results and comparative data for designated equivalent methods for sulfur dioxide. EPA-600/4-84-015, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Research Triangle Park, NC 27711. 1984 January.
2. de Boor, C. A Practical Guide to Splines. New York: Springer-Verlag; 1978. 392 p.
3. Smit, H. C. The use of Kalman filtering and correlation techniques in analytical calibration procedures. Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards 90(6): 441-450; 1985 November-December.
4. Velleman, P. F. Definition and comparison of robust nonlinear data smoothing algorithms. Journal of the American Statistical Association 75(371): 609-615; 1980 September.
5. Filliben, J. J. The probability plot correlation coefficient test for normality. Technometrics 17(1): 111-117; 1975 February.
6. Tick, L. J.; Shaman, P. Sampling rates and appearance of stationary Gaussian processes. Technometrics 8(1): 91-106; 1966 February.
7. Thomson, D. J. Spectrum estimation techniques for characterization and development of WT4 waveguide--I and II. Bell System Technical Journal 56(9): 1769-1815 and 56(10) 1983-2005; 1977 November and December.
8. Bloomfield, P. Fourier analysis of time series: An introduction. New York: John Wiley and Sons; 1976. 258 p.
9. Khatrı, C. G. Distribution of the largest or the smallest characteristic root under null hypothesis concerning complex multivariate normal populations. Annals of Mathematical Statistics 35(6): 1807-1810; 1964.
10. Abramowitz, M; Stegun, I. A. Handbook of mathematical functions. Nat. Bur. Stand. (U.S.) Appl. Math. Ser. 55; 1964 June. 1046 p.
11. Liggett, W. S. A test for serial correlation in multivariate data. Annals of Statistics 5(2): 408-413; 1977.
12. Box, G. E. P.; Jenkins, G. M. Time series analysis forecasting and control. San Francisco: Holden-Day; 1970. 553 p.